

Crop management

Environmental limitations to rice cultivation in the Punjab

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Five sites representing typical rice-growing areas of the Punjab were selected to evaluate suitability for rice production. On the basis of soil-site

characteristics (see table), four suitability classes have been defined, from highly suitable to currently not suitable.

Average rice yields under controlled conditions with fertilizer (50-12-12 kg NPK/ha) based on soil test suggest that the yield data correlate well with soil-site suitability class.

The yield potential of rice soils in the Punjab is controlled by rainfall during growing season, soil texture, drainage, infiltration, soil reaction, and soluble salts. It is possible to make yield predictions at different levels of the suitability class on the basis of soil-site

characteristics and their degree of limitation. The study predicts the following environmental limitations for sustained rice cultivation:

- Rainfall—less than 300 mm during growing season Jul-Sep is limiting.
- Soil type—fine loamy surface and subsurface texture with more than 16% clay.
- Drainage—optimum from moderately well to imperfectly drained.
- Soil reaction—optimum pH 7-8.3.
- Soluble salts—salinity and alkalinity are the primary obstacles. □

Soil and site suitability characteristics and their limitations.^a Ludhiana, India.

Soil	Rainfall (mm) Jul-Sep (annual)	Water intake (mm) cumulative 6h	Drainage	pH	ECe 10 ⁻³ dS/m	Exchangeable sodium percentage	Silt	Clay	Organic C (%)	Overall limitation	Land suitability class ^b	Yield (t/ha)	
												Control	Recommended fertilizer based on soil-test ^c
Rawalpindi clay loam (Aquic Ustochrepts)	202 (315)	29	Imperfect	8.6 (8.4)	1.6 (1.7)	15.6 (9.3)	41.5 (33.0)	30.0 (34.1)	0.45 (0.22)	1-2	S2	3.7	6.1
Degree of limitation	2	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	0				
Samana sandy loam (Udic Ustochrepts)	474 (680)	58	Well	7.4 (7.6)	1.0 (0.7)	6.9 (6.6)	18.8 (29.9)	12.7 (15.7)	0.35 (0.17)	2-3	S3	2.8	5.1
Degree of limitation	0	3	3	0	0	0	2	2	1				
Bhoewal loam (Typic Haplustalfs)	532 (713)	42	Moderately well	7.4 (8.2)	1.0 (0.8)	7.4 (8.2)	50.3 (48.8)	25.9 (29.2)	0.72 (0.26)	0-1	S1	4.6	7.8
Degree of limitation	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Narrike sandy loam (Natraqic Calciorthid)	290 (425)	40	Moderately well	9.4 (9.3)	2.4 (3.6)	40 (43)	20.6 (29.7)	18.2 (22.8)	0.17 (0.12)	3-4	S4	1.2	1.7
Degree of limitation	2	1	1	4	3	4	0	1	2				
Gurdaspur loam (Udic Haplustalfs)	603 (88.6)	48	Moderately well	7.2 (7.3)	0.4 (0.4)	2.5 (1.1)	30.6 (40.7)	10.4 (15.7)	0.59 (0.29)	1-2	S1-2	4.1	7.4
Degree of limitation	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0				

^aValues in brackets indicate weighted mean of the column. ^bS1 = highly suitable, S4 = currently not suitable. ^cAverage of 5 yr.

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Effect of farmyard manure (FYM) supplemented with N, P, K on grain yield

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FYM is an important source of plant

nutrients for irrigated rice in Bhutan. In the Wangdiphodrang-Punakha valley, FYM is predominantly composed of animal manures mixed with rice straw in various stages of decomposition. An estimated average of 7 t FYM (fresh weight)/ha is applied before transplanting. The actual rate varies widely, from zero to 20 t/ha.

As fertilizer-responsive rice varieties become more widespread, FYM

probably will continue to contribute significantly to crop nutrition and soil condition.

We supplemented FYM with N, P, K to evaluate its effect on grain yield of IR36. IR36 seedlings raised in dry bed nurseries were transplanted in mid-Jun at 49 d after seeding with 20- × 20-cm spacing in 4- × 6-m banded plots, in a completely randomized block design with 7 treatments and 3 replications.

The soil was a loam with pH 6.6, 1.2% organic C, 9.3 meq CEC/100 g, 4.6 ppm available P (Olsen's), 0.332 meq

K/100 g, and 1.2 ppm available Zn. The FYM contained 1.8% N and 0.45 ppm total P. FYM, all P and K, and 35 kg N/ha were applied basally; the remaining N was topdressed at panicle initiation. Grain yield was computed at 14% moisture.

No significant pest or disease damage or water stress occurred during crop development. All fertilizer treatments increased yield significantly (see table). Mean yield from plots given FYM alone was 20% higher than check plots. Supplementing FYM with extra N had no effect. FYM plus P significantly increased yield 18% over FYM alone. Yields with FYM supplemented with

N+P and from plots fertilized with N+P or N+P+K only did not differ significantly from yields with FYM+P.

The results indicate that utilization of nitrogen in FYM may be seriously limited by inadequate soil P. In Wangdiphodrang-Punakha, soil analyses now show that available P levels are generally low (less than 10 ppm). Available K and other plant nutrients appear to be adequate. These preliminary results suggest that in a region where use of inorganic fertilizer is very low but use of FYM is routine, more benefit could be obtained from supplementing FYM with P. □

Effect of FYM supplemented with N and P on yield of IR36. CARD, Wangdiphodrang, Bhutan, 1986.

FYM ^b (t/ha)	Fertilizer treatment ^a			Grain yield ^c (t/ha)
	N (kg/ha)	P (kg/ha)	K (kg/ha)	
0	0	0	0	4.8 c
7.5	0	0	0	5.8 b
7.5	35	0	0	5.3 bc
7.5	0	50	0	6.9 a
7.5	35	50	0	7.0 a
0	75	50	0	6.6 a
0	75	50	40	6.9 a
	CV (%)			4.5

^a N as urea, P as single superphosphate, K as muriate of potash. ^b Fresh weight. ^c Mean separation in a column by DMRT at the 5% level.

Phosphorus requirements in a rice - wheat cropping system

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We studied P requirements of rice grown in sequence with wheat in the field 1983 to 1987. Different combinations of P level (0, 13, and 26 kg P/ha) and P application (applying P to rice alone, wheat alone, or both rice and wheat) were laid out in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

At the beginning of the experiment in 1983, the soil (sandy loam, Typic Ustochrept) had pH 8.1, 0.29% organic C, and 14.5 kg Olsen's P/ha. All plots received 120 kg N and 23 kg K/ha. All

Influence of P on rice yield in a rice - wheat cropping system. Punjab, India, 1983-87.

P (kg/ha)		Grain yield (t/ha)					
Rice	Wheat	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	Mean 1984-87
0	0	7.4	5.7	6.2	6.4	5.6	6.0
13	0	7.3	6.8	7.2	8.4	8.4	7.7
26	0	7.5	6.9	7.2	8.4	8.6	7.8
0	13	7.5	6.0	6.5	7.2	6.8	6.6
0	26	6.8	6.0	6.5	7.3	7.6	6.8
13	13	7.1	6.7	7.4	8.3	8.5	7.7
13	26	7.5	6.8	7.2	8.4	8.6	7.8
26	13	7.0	6.8	7.1	8.3	8.5	7.7
26	26	7.5	6.6	7.1	7.9	7.4	7.2
LSD (0.05)		ns	0.7	0.4	0.9	0.7	0.7

P and K and 1/3 N were applied before transplanting. The remaining N was applied at 21 d and 42 d after transplanting.

Rice responded significantly to direct application of up to 13 kg P/ha (see

table). Rice grown on the residue of 25 kg P/ha applied to the preceding wheat showed no response. Increasing P to 26 kg/ha for both rice and wheat slightly depressed rice yield. □

Effect of two phosphorus sources with or without azolla incorporation on rice yield in the Senegal River valley

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We compared a soluble-type P (triple superphosphate with 45% P₂O₅) and a natural type P (aluminum phosphate

Soil analysis. Fanaye P4 (Paleustollic Torrerts), Fanaye Station, Senegal.

pH		Texture ^a	Clay (%)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Organic matter ^b (%)	CEC ^c (meq/100 g)	Available P BRAY II (ppm)	Total P ^d (ppm)	Adsorbed P ^e at 0.2 ppm P in the soil solution (µg P/g of soil)
Soil:water (1:1)	KCl 1 N									
6.2	4.4	Clay	46.5	29.9	23.6	0.35	31.26	1.50	240	330

^a Bouyoucos method. ^b Walkley - Black method. ^c Cobaltihexamine method (Orsini et Remy 1976). ^d Perchloric acid digestion. ^e Fox and Kamprath method (1970).

with 34% P₂O₅). We also evaluated the influence of azolla incorporation on assimilation of P by rice.

The trial for four consecutive cropping seasons was conducted on a fine clayey soil Paleustollic Torrerts (see